

An efficient conversion of β -phenylisoserine to β -hydroxyphenylalanine derivatives via aziridines

Jyoti Prokash Nandi, Biswajit Saha, Seema Sharma, Susmita Bose and Javed Iqbal*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-208 016, India

Manuscript received 12 October 1999

β -Phenylisoserine derivatives can be treated with DEAD (diethyl azodicarboxylate)/PPh₃ to afford aziridines which can be regioselectively opened with oxygen nucleophiles in the presence of catalytic amount of *para*-toluenesulfonic acid to give the corresponding β -substituted phenylalanine derivatives in good yields. The generality of this transformation is illustrated by converting β -phenylisoserine derived dipeptides to the corresponding β -hydroxyphenylalanine containing dipeptides.

Peptides and their analogs have long been used in medicinal chemistry as therapeutical agents which mainly function by causing a disruption¹ of interplay between messenger molecule or enzyme substrates and their targets. However, due to their enzymatic degradation and low oral bioavailability, peptides are not very effective as inhibitors or drugs. As a result, molecules that can mimic the structural and functional aspects of peptides, known as *peptidomimetics*, have become immensely important to both medicinal and organic chemists. *Peptidomimetics* are tailor-made molecules, the structural profile of which lies² between a slightly altered peptide on one side and non-peptide on the other. Modification of the side-chains of natural α -amino acid residue constitutes an important route to the mimics of peptides. Thus replacement of a natural side-chain with that of an unnatural one in peptides derived from natural amino acids leads to molecules with interesting biological properties and such structures^{1d} have been incorporated as core units in several enzyme inhibitors in which the modified side-chain is generally found to be responsible for the bioactive conformation. The modification of a side-chain, when it is part of a peptide, offers an attractive protocol for accessing peptides with diverse structural profiles. We now demonstrate that *anti*- β -phenylisoserine derivatives **1** can be smoothly transformed to the corresponding *anti*- β -substituted phenylalanine derivatives **3** by acid-catalyzed opening of the intermediate aziridine **2** with oxygen or sulfur nucleophiles (Scheme 1).

Aziridines **2** can be efficiently accessed from the corresponding *anti*- β -phenylisoserine derivative **1** by DEAD PPh₃ promoted cyclization³. The *anti*- β -phenylisoserine derivatives **1** can be prepared by our cobalt-catalyzed opening of epoxides as reported⁴ earlier. The reaction of aziridine **2a** (obtained from **1**, Ar = 4-BrC₆H₄ **1a**) with various nu-

cleophiles is presented in Scheme 2. Thus the *para*-toluenesulfonic acid catalyzed reaction⁵ of **2a** in water-THF mixture resulted in a regioselective opening to afford the *anti*- β -hydroxyphenylalanine derivative **3a** in excellent yields. Similarly, the opening of aziridine **2a** in the pres-

Scheme 1

ence of catalytic *para*-toluenesulfonic acid and methanol and benzyl alcohol gave the corresponding *anti*- β -alkoxyphenylalanine derivatives **3b** and **3c**, respectively. Interestingly, the aziridine can be regio-selectively opened with thiophenol in the presence of catalytic amount of cobalt(II) chloride to afford⁶ the *anti*- β -thiophenoxyphe-nylalanine derivative **3d** in good yields. The latter reaction was found to be sluggish in the absence of cobalt(II) chloride. The corresponding *syn*-diastereomers were obtained in trace amount in these reactions.

These transformations can also be performed on the aziridine peptides **5a-c**, which can be prepared from **4** on cyclization according to the procedure described above (PPh₃/DEAD). The aziridine peptides **5** were transformed to the corresponding *anti*- β -hydroxyphenylalanine derivatives **6** on treatment under aqueous acidic condition in a highly regioselective manner in good to excellent yields (Table 1). Thus the *para*-toluenesulfonic acid catalyzed opening of aziridine dipeptides **5a-c** in water-THF mixture afforded the corresponding β -hydroxyphenylalanine dipeptide derivatives **6a-c** in good yields. These dipeptides were isolated by column chromatography as single diastereomers in high chemical purity (HPLC). However, the absolute con-

† Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th birth anniversary

Scheme 2

figuration for the β -hydroxyphenylalanine residue in **6** could not be determined and only the relative configuration for it is presented in Table 1.

The *anti*-stereostructure in **3a** was confirmed by converting it to the corresponding aziridine **2a** on treatment with CCl_4 , PPh_3 and Et_3N (Scheme 3). This result also supports the *anti*-stereochemistry of β -hydroxyphenylalanine derivatives **6** which have the same relative stereochemistry as **3a** (the proton NMR chemical shift⁷ and coupling constant for the $-\text{CHOH}$ are similar in both **3a** and **6a-c**, re-

spectively). The high regio- and stereoselectivity obtained for these openings may be understood by the attack of nucleophile on a solvent stabilized non-symmetric carbocation as the latter may be formed subsequent to the protonation of the aziridine nitrogen.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated that *anti*- β -phenylisoserine derived dipeptides can be efficiently transformed to the corresponding aziridine peptides on treatment with DEAD and PPh_3 or Et_3N . These aziridine peptides are converted regio- and stereoselectively to the corresponding

Table 1. Synthesis of β -hydroxyphenylalanine derivatives from β -phenylisoserine derivatives via aziridine

^aYield of the isolated product based ^bOnly the relative stereochemistry for 4-6 is given here

anti- β -hydroxyphenylalanine derived dipeptides by acid-catalyzed solvolysis in nearly quantitative yields. The transformation of β -phenylisoserine to β -substituted phenylala-

Scheme 3

nine derived dipeptides introduces an additional level of diversity and therefore this protocol is suitable for the synthesis of library of compounds by a combinatorial approach. We are currently developing this protocol for a combinatorial synthesis of β -substituted phenylalanine derived dipeptides from aziridines.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank D.S.T., New Delhi, for the financial assistance to this project.

References

- (a) R. M. J. Liskamp, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1994, **113**, 1; (b) A. Giannis and T. Kolter, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1993, **32**, 1244; (c) R. A. Wiley and D. A. Rich, *Med. Res. Rev.*, 1993, **13**, 327; (d) J. Gante, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1994, **33**, 1699; (e) V. J. Hruby, *Biopolymers*, 1993, **33**, 1073.
- (a) G. Jung and A. G. Beck-Sickinger, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1992, **31**, 367; (b) D. Jaio, K. C. Russel and V. J. Hruby, *Tetrahedron*, 1993, **49**, 3511; (c) W. J. Moree, L. C. van Gent, G. A. van der Marcel and R. M. J. Liskamp, *Tetrahedron*, 1993, **49**, 1133; (d) T. Gordon, P. Hansen, B. Morgan, J. Singh, E. Baizman and S. Ward, *Biorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 1991, **1**, 653.
- General procedure for DEAD- PPh_3 promoted aziridine formation: A mixture of *anti*-amino alcohol (1 mmol), DEAD (3 mmol)

and PPh_3 (3.2 mmol) or PPh_3 (3 mmol), CCl_4 (3 mmol) and Et_3N (7 mmol) dissolved in acetonitrile (25 ml) and was stirred at room temperature for 20–25 h. The removal of solvent under vacuum gave a residue which was chromatographed on silica gel to afford the aziridines in good yields.

- (a) B. C. Das and J. Iqbal *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 1235; (b) T. Punniyamurthy and J. Iqbal, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 2903; (c) A. De, P. Basak and J. Iqbal, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 8383.
- General procedure for acid-catalyzed opening of aziridines: Aziridine (2 mmol) and *para*-toluenesulfonic acid (5 mol%) were taken in THF-water (80 : 20) or alcohol and stirred at room temperature for 10 h. The removal of solvent under vacuum gave a residue which was extracted with ethyl acetate (3×15 ml) and the extract washed with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate and water. Drying (MgSO_4) and evaporation of solvent gave a residue which on column chromatography (SiO_2) afforded the β -hydroxy- or β -alkoxyphenylalanine derivatives 3a-c or 6a-c, respectively, as solid.
- Cobalt(II) chloride catalyzed opening of aziridine with thiophenol: A mixture of aziridine (2 mmol), thiophenol (2 mmol), cobalt(II) chloride (5 mol%) dissolved in acetonitrile (20 ml) was stirred at room temperature under N_2 atmosphere for 10 h. Removal of the solvent gave a residue which was taken in ethyl acetate (20 ml) and washed with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate and water. Drying (MgSO_4) and evaporation of solvent gave a residue which on column chromatography afforded β -thiophenoxyphenylalanine derivative 3d as solid.
- Proton NMR and Mass of some compounds: 3a; NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.34–7.39 (5H, m), 7.24 (2H, m), 6.57 (2H, m), 5.18 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 4.53 (1H, bd), 4.37 (1H, dd, J 13.5 and 6.5 Hz), 4.07 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 1.07 (3H, t, J 6.8 Hz), m/z 365 ($M+1$)⁺, 259, 257, 230, 228, 186, 184, 157, 155, 107, 105, 79, 77; 6c: NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.11–7.39 (8H, m), 6.82 (1H, m), 6.55 (2H, m), 5.05 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 4.52 (1H, dd, J 8 and 3 Hz), 4.23 (1H, d, J 5 Hz), 4.02 (2H, bs), 3.70 (3H, s), 2.09 (1H, m), 0.82 (3H, d, J 6.8 Hz), 0.69 (3H, d, J 7.2 Hz), m/z 370 (M^+), 352, 263, 202, 193, 132, 104, 84, 77.

